

A study of process variables for the photo-catalytic degradation of rhodamine-B using TiO₂ and Nb₂O₅

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Abstract : This study involves the photo-catalytic degradation of rhodamine-B (RB) employing heterogeneous photo-catalytic process. Photo-catalytic activity of different semiconductors such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and niobium pentaoxide (Nb₂O₅) has been investigated. An attempt has been made to study the effect of process parameters through amount of catalyst, initial concentration of dye, and operating pH on photo-catalytic degradation of RB. The experiments were carried out by varying pH (2–11), amount of catalyst (0.25–1.5 g/L), and initial concentration of dye (10–50 mg/L). The optimum catalyst dose was found to be 1 g/L of TiO₂ and 1.25 g/L of Nb₂O₅ for RB at 30 mg/L respectively. The maximum rate of degradation was observed in acidic medium at pH 3 for catalyst TiO₂ and Nb₂O₅ respectively. It was observed that the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ is greater than Nb₂O₅.

Keywords : Photo-catalysis, photo-catalytic degradation, dyes, rhodamine-B, TiO₂, Nb₂O₅.

Introduction

Textile industries produce large volume of colored dye effluents which are toxic and non-biodegradable. The contamination of water supplies by organic molecules is an increasing problem mainly because many of these molecules are not readily degraded by conventional methods for the treatment of effluents¹. This problem has increased with the development of the textile industry because many of the pollutants are dyes used by them. Besides causing visual pollution, this kind of pollutant has high levels of toxicity, non-biodegradability and resistance to destruction².

The main technologies available for the treatment of dyes involve the transfer of the pollutant from a liquid phase to another phase, concentrating the dye on an adsorbent, for example, so that it can later be discarded in a landfill or incinerated. This phase exchange is not an ideal remedy; destructive oxidation treatments provide more permanent solutions³. An alternative for the removal of dyes is photo-catalytic degradation. This kind of process enables the complete destruction of the pollutant and

has been studied thoroughly during the past many years, especially for liquid and gaseous effluents⁴. The photo catalyzed degradation of a dye in solution is initiated by the photo excitation of the semiconductor, followed by the formation of electron hole pair on the surface of catalyst (eq. 1). The high oxidative potential of the hole (h^+_{VB}) in the catalyst permits the direct oxidation of the dye to reactive intermediates (eq. 2).

Metal oxide

Another reactive intermediate which is responsible for the degradation is hydroxyl radical (OH^{*}). It is either formed by the decomposition of water (eq. 3) or by reaction of the hole with OH⁻ (eq. 4). The hydroxyl radical is an extremely strong, non-selective oxidant ($E^\circ = +3.06$ V), which leads to the partial or complete mineralization of several organic chemicals^{5,6}.

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is generally considered to be the best photo-catalyst and has the ability to detoxify water from a number of organic pollutants. However widespread use of TiO₂ is uneconomical for large-scale water treatment, thereby interest of researchers toward the search for suitable alternatives to TiO₂^{6,7}. Many attempts have been made to study photo-catalytic activity of different semiconductors such as SnO₂, ZrO₂, CdS and Nb₂O₅^{8,9}, compared the photo-catalytic activity of TiO₂, SnO₂, ZnS, Nb₂O₅ and CdS for the degradation of rhodamine-B dye and found TiO₂ to be the most effective catalyst for the degradation of dyes. However, compared with other photo-catalysts, the photo-catalytic activity of niobium pentaoxide (Nb₂O₅) for oxidizing organic contaminants in water has been less reported¹⁰.

Experimental

Systems requirement :

Chemicals :

Titanium dioxide (99.7%) and niobium pentaoxide (99.9%) was used as a photo-catalyst and purchased from Molychem, India. Rhodamine-B dye used in this research was purchased from Merck, India. The molecular structure and other properties of dye are given in Table 1. Distilled water was used for preparation of various solutions. pH of the solutions was adjusted with 1 N H₂SO₄ or 1 N NaOH. All others chemical used were of technical grade.

Table 1. Characteristics of RB dye

Chemical structure	
Symbol	RB
Molecular formula	C ₂₈ H ₃₁ ClN ₂ O ₃
Molar mass	479.02
Solubility in water	50 g/L
Appearance	Red to violet powder

Experimental setup and procedure :

The photo-catalytic degradation was carried out in specially designed batch reactor as shown in Fig. 1. The light source was 8 W UV lamp (Philips) 254 wavelengths. The photo-catalytic reactor consists of cylindrical vessels

Fig. 1. Actual setup of photo-catalytic reactor.

330 mm length and 70 mm diameter with the condensation system, along with the inside tube of 330 mm length and 30 mm diameter and closing cap of 335 mm diameter which is made of quartz. The following figures show the actual setup of photo-catalytic reactor.

The experimental setup has been shown in Fig. 2. For the degradation experiments, fixed amount of photo catalyst Nb₂O₅/TiO₂ was added to 500 ml of 30 ppm solution of dye in each run at definite pH. The suspension was subjected to irradiation under UV light and stirring with

Fig. 2. Actual experimental set-up.

help of magnetic stirrer for a fixed interval of time. At different time intervals, a sample was taken out with the help of a pipette and then centrifuged to remove the catalyst. The percentage degradation was calculated as follows : % Degradation = $100 \times (C_0 - C)/C_0$, where C_0 = initial concentration of dye solution, C = concentration of dye solution after photo-irradiation.

Analytical methods :

UV-Visible spectrophotometer : The following Fig. 3 shows the Perkin-Elmer made LAMBDA 35 UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Fig. 3. UV spectrophotometer.

Results and discussion

Photo-catalytic degradation of RD using TiO₂ and Nb₂O₅ :

The experiments were carried out to study the degradation of RB employing TiO₂/Nb₂O₅ as catalyst in presence of UV light. Various parameters which affect the degradation efficiency such as catalyst loading (0.25–1.5 g/L), pH (2–11), initial concentration of dye (10–50 mg/L), were studied varying the above parameters in presence of UV light.

Effect of amount of catalyst :

Figs. (4a and 4b) and (5a and 5b) show the effect of catalyst loading (TiO₂ and Nb₂O₅) on the degradation of RB. It can be seen that initial slopes of the curves increase greatly by increasing catalyst loading (TiO₂ and Nb₂O₅) from 0.25 to 1.5 g/L for RB, thereafter the rate of degradation remains constant. Further increase in the dose of catalyst had no effect on degradation of dyes. The photo-catalytic destruction of other organic pollutants has also exhibited the same dependence on catalyst dose¹¹.

Fig. 4. Effect of TiO₂ dose on degradation rate of RB dye at initial dye concentration (30 mg/L).

This can be explained on the basis that optimum catalyst loading is found to be dependent on initial solute concentration because with the increase in catalyst dosage, total active surface area increases, hence availability of more active sites on catalyst surface¹². At the same time, due to an increase in turbidity of the suspension with high dose of photo-catalyst, there will be decrease in penetration of UV light and hence photo-activated volume of suspension decreases¹³. Thus it can be concluded that higher dose of catalyst may not be useful both in view of aggregation as well as reduced irradiation field due to light scattering. Therefore the catalyst doses 1 g/L of TiO₂ and 1.25 g/L Nb₂O₅ were fixed for RB, respectively for further studies.

Fig. 5. Effect of Nb_2O_5 dose on degradation rate of RB dye at initial dye concentration (30 mg/L).

Fig. 6. Effect of initial concentration of RB dye on percentage degradation at TiO_2 dose 1 g/L.

Effect of concentration of dye :

After optimizing the catalyst dose 1 g/L of TiO_2 and 1.25 g/L Nb_2O_5 for RB, the photo-catalytic degradation of dye was carried out by varying the initial concentrations of the dye from 10 to 50 mg/L in order to assess the appropriate amount of catalyst dose. As the concentration of the dye was increased, the rate of degradation decreased. Figs. (6a and 6b) and (7a and 7b) shows the degradation of RB at different concentrations of dye solutions (10–50 mg/L). In the case of 1 g/L of TiO_2 and 1.25 g/L Nb_2O_5 catalyst loading for RB, for dye solutions of 10 mg/L maximum degradation occurred. The possible explanation for this behavior is that as the initial

concentration of the dye increases, the path length of the photons entering the solution decreases and in low concentration the reverse effect is observed, thereby increasing the number of photon absorption by the catalyst in lower concentration. Therefore the dye concentrations 30 mg/L was fixed for further studies.

Effect of pH :

Wastewater containing dyes is discharged at different pH; therefore it is important to study the role of pH on degradation of dye. In order to study the effect of pH on the degradation efficiency, experiments were carried out at various pH values, ranging from 2 to 11 for constant

Fig. 7. Effect of initial concentration of RB dye on percentage degradation at Nb_2O_5 dose 1.25 g/L.

Fig. 8. Effect of pH on degradation rate of RB dye (TiO_2 dose - 1 g/L, dye initial concentration - 30 mg/L).

dye concentration (30 mg/L) and catalyst loading 1 g/L TiO_2 and 1.25 g/L Nb_2O_5 , respectively. Figs. (8a and 8b) and (9a and 9b) shows the degradation efficiency of RB as a function of pH. It has been observed that the degradation efficiency initially increases with increase in pH and then decreases with increase in pH, exhibiting maximum rate of degradation at pH 3 in case of catalyst loading (1 g/L TiO_2) and at 30 mg/L dye concentration. And the degradation efficiency decrease with increases in pH, exhibiting maximum rate of degradation at pH 3 in case of catalyst loading (1.25 g/L Nb_2O_5) and at 30 mg/L dye concentration.

Conclusion

Process variables, such as initial dye concentration, pH, and catalyst concentration significantly affect the photo-activated process. These processes were efficient in the degradation of RB. Experimental results indicate that the degradation of dyes is facilitated in the presence of catalyst. Comparison of photo-catalytic activity of different semiconductors has clearly indicated that the TiO_2 is better than the Nb_2O_5 photo-catalyst for degradation of RB. Besides higher efficiency, the other advantage of TiO_2 is its low cost than the Nb_2O_5 . The initial rate of degradation increased with increase in catalyst dose up to an optimum loading. Further increase in catalyst dose

Fig. 9. Effect of pH on degradation rate of RB dye (Nb_2O_5 dose -1.25 g/L, dye initial concentration - 30 mg/L).

showed no effect. As the initial concentration of dyes was increased, the rate of degradation decreased.

References

1. P. R. Gogate and A. B. Pandit, *Adv. Environ. Res.*, 2004, **8**, 501.
2. J. Wu and T. Zhang, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2004, **162**, 171.
3. R. W. Matthews, *Water Research*, 1991, **25**, 1169.
4. J. Liqiang, S. Xiaojun, S. Jing, C. Weimin, X. Zili, D. Yaoguo and F. Honggang, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 2003, **79**, 133.
5. D. Yu, R. Cai and Z. Liu, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A : Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2004, **60**, 1617.
6. A. L. Pruden and D. F. Ollis, *J. Catal.*, 1983, **82**, 404.
7. K. Vinodgopal, S. Hotchandani and P. V. Kamat, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 9040.
8. H. Hidaka, J. Zhao, E. Pelizzetti and N. Serpone, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 2226.
9. Gaoke Zhang, Jie Gong, Xi Zou, Fangsheng He, Hao Zhang, Qiang Zhang, Ying Liu, Xia Yang and Bo Hu, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2006, **123**, 59.
10. Y. Ma and J. Yao, *Chemosphere*, 1999, **38**, 2407.
11. Y. Ma and J. Yao, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1998, **116**, 167.
12. Sushil Kumar Kansal, Navjeet Kaur and Sukhmehar Singh, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.*, 2009, **4**, 709.
13. E. T. Soares, M. A. Lansarin and C. C. Moro, *Brazilian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 2007, **24**, 29.